

2020 Ohio State Department of Physics Summer Research Program Final Report: Autoencoders for Trigger-Level Analysis

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Introduction

One of the large barriers to the information recording of proton-proton collision events at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) is storage. Currently the ATLAS experiment implements a trigger system to reduce the number of events saved. The two step system rejects events below a certain transverse momentum and reduces the data rate from approximately 40MHz to 1kHz. If new physics is present, especially in low mass ($<1\text{TeV}$) regions, then it might be discarded, reducing sensitivity. The Trigger-Level Analysis (TLA) searches circumvent these restrictions by only saving event information available to the High Level Trigger, heavily reducing the data per event, see figure 1 of [1]. To further increase data taking rates in future searches, new techniques are necessary. Autoencoder Neural Networks are one such technique.

Autoencoders (AEs) are deep neural networks that attempt to replicate the input and is composed of three parts: the encoder, latent space, and decoder. The latent space is a hidden layer with less dimensions than the input and output, meaning that this representation of the data is smaller than the original. The encoder compresses the input to the latent space and decoder the opposite. This architecture makes them a natural choice for data compression as a sufficiently good encoder could compress data and save it to be decompressed by the decoder later.

This work sought to understand the viability of AEs for data compression in future analyses, particularly dijet TLA. As such, events of two jets were used for training and validation. For an autoencoder to be used, it must not reconstruct bad jets as good ones and vice versa. This phenomenon, known as threshold migration, was the primary focus of this study.

Architecture and Data

There are 27 single dimensional variables used by the High-Level Trigger, and those are the ones used by TLA, and were the inputs and outputs of the network. These include the four-momentum of the jet and a set of calorimeter variables characterizing the jet quality. Jets used for training and validation were the two hardest from events passing the TLA selection cut: lead $p_T > 185\text{ GeV}$, sublead $p_T > 85\text{ GeV}$ and $|y^*| < .3$. As the variables had significantly different distributions,

filtering and normalization was required for the data. The network is composed of 7 fully-connected hidden layers containing 200 nodes each, with a latent space of 14 nodes. This gives a compression ratio close to 2:1. The activation function for all nodes was a Leaky ReLU.

The data used in this study were taken from run 364292. For training and validation, about a million jets were required, which necessitated using about $\frac{2}{3}$ of the run. Training and validation data was split 80-20. An independent testing data set was made from one of the files not used for training, made of around 200,000 jets.

Neural network performance is highly sensitive to distributions of input variables. To maximize performance, filtering and normalization must be employed. The filtering was reused from Eric Wulff's thesis [2] and can be seen here, and was designed to remove significant outliers. As this work only considered the two hardest jets, compared with all jets from an event used in [2], so some filters are redundant. Some of these filters were criteria for "Bad Loose jets" and as such removed jets that would be useful for testing threshold migration. Future work could set stricter limits on some variables for training, and relax them for testing.

The normalization was also reused from previous work. The scheme either rescaled the distribution by a factor or took the logarithm of the data, to reduce the range to within an order of magnitude. The variables that were logged were Negative Energy, mass, Leading Cluster Center and Second Lambda, Leading Cluster Second R, Average LAr Quality Factor, p_T , Leading Cluster p_T , Centroid R, and the Out of Timing Variables. The details of the normalization can be seen here.

To understand the impact of the normalization and filtering, networks were trained on data that had not been normalized or filtered. The normalization however, requires some variables to be shifted to prevent negative numbers as inputs to logarithms. A minimal filtering scheme was made that only removed events to allow normalization to take place. The variables filtered in the minimal filtering were Leading Cluster p_T and the out of timing variables.

Autoencoders rely on learning patterns between variables in the data, so preserving and strengthening correlations that exist is important for maximizing performance. As can be seen in figures 2 and 3. the normalization and filtering increased correlations between many of the variables, increasing performance.

Training and Network Performance

All training took place on HTCondor. Utilizing a single GPU, training lasted usually between four and six hours. The networks were trained on 100 epochs with a batch size of 4096 jets. The learning rate and weight decay were 10^{-2} . Mean Square Error (MSE) was used as the loss function. Five networks were considered over this study, each with different combinations of normalization and filtering. The

results of network performance can be seen in Figures 3-6. The full filtering improved performance by $O(10^5)$ and normalization $O(10^9)$. Any overtraining that occurred in other networks was eliminated with both the normalization and filtering applied.

Results

Jets are one of the more complex decay products to study in high-energy collisions. The fragmentation of decay products lead to large uncertainties in the resolution of jet measurements. As such, there need to be thresholds set to determine whether jets are of high quality, suitable for analysis. The standard criteria for a bad jet can be seen at the end of the section. Criteria 4 and 5 are not considered in this study as tracking information and f_{max} are not saved for trigger-level jets. If AEs are to be used for reconstructing events, then they must not reconstruct bad jets as good ones and vice versa. To study this, a trained network is given an independent data set to reconstruct. Then the jet quality criteria are applied to both the input and output. If the jet is considered a bad jet in the input, a perfect autoencoder would reconstruct it as one. In the plots on pages nine and ten, any jets in the off-diagonal bins indicate mismatches between the autoencoder reconstruction and the input. The statistics of this are limited because the filtering already removes some bad jets. In the more statistically limited variables, anywhere from 5-50% of the jets are reconstructed incorrectly. Using a independent data set that doesn't have the bad jets filtered out would reduce this error, and would be one of the first steps in future work. The variables with significant jets around the threshold, $|\eta| < 2$, 2.8 and HEC Fraction = .5, have a reconstruction error of 1-4%. This is expected as more jets for training and validation are present in this region, so the network gets more training to reconstruct them accurately.

1. $f_{HEC} > 0.5$ and $|f_Q^{HEC}| > 0.5$ and $\langle Q \rangle > 0.8$
2. $|E_{neg}| > 60$ GeV
3. $f_{EM} > 0.95$ and $f_Q^{LAr} > 0.8$ and $\langle Q \rangle > 0.8$ and $|\eta| < 2.8$
4. $f_{max} > 0.99$ and $|\eta| < 2$
5. $f_{EM} < 0.05$ and $f_{ch} < 0.05$ and $|\eta| < 2$
6. $f_{EM} < 0.05$ and $|\eta| \geq 2$

Conclusions and Future Work

The viability of autoencoder neural networks for data compression in future analyses was investigated. Autoencoders are a natural choice for data compression as they contain a layer smaller than the input and output that can be used as a compressed representation. To understand how effective this technique is, the reconstruction of jet quality variables around their respective thresholds was evaluated.

The network successfully reconstructed jets near the threshold between 1-50% of the time, with most of these values strongly limited by statistics. The variables with a large amount of jets around the threshold reconstructed them incorrectly only 1-4% of the time.

A first step in continuing this work is evaluating the network with data that are less filtered, allowing for better statistics of bad jet reconstruction. To improve performance of the network, stricter filtering could be applied, as the signal selection removes many bad jets. New normalization schemes could also be investigated, including mapping all variables onto a single range, or utilizing a reparameterization layer. Another topic of interest is utilizing a custom loss function that takes threshold migration into account.

References

1. ATLAS Collaboration, Search for Low-Mass Dijet Resonances Using Trigger-Level Jets with the ATLAS Detector in pp Collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV Phys. Rev. Lett. 121, 081801
2. Wulff, Eric (2020) *Deep Autoencoders for Compression in High Energy Physics*, [Master's Dissertation, Lund University] <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/9004751>

Appendix A: How to Use the Code

Setting up the Environment

Note: To train networks and get ATLAS data, one must have access to lxplus and have a valid grid certificate.

1. Login to lxplus on the terminal by

```
ssh CERNusername@lxplus.cern.ch
```

and enter your password when prompted

2. Follow the directions here: https://github.com/Autoencoders-compression-anomaly/AE-Compression-pytorch/tree/Sam_dev

Training a Network

1. Having logged into lxplus as above, setup the ATLAS software with

setupATLAS

2. Navigate to where you want the raw data stored and create a directory:

```
mkdir AE-trainingData
```

. This should be somewhere with at least a few GB's of space, the afs work directory is a good choice

3. Download the ATLAS jet data, containing jets from 2018. Hopefully soon data will be released publicly per <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2745133> negating the need for an ATLAS membership
4. Navigate to the process_data directory in AE-Compression
5. Due to unresolved packaging issues, to apply the TLA selection cut, make sure you are not in any virtual environments and use python 2.7, as it contains both pandas and ROOT
6. If using multiple ROOT files, uncomment the for loop and comment the other definition of the files variable out. Change path_to_data to the appropriate path and run.
7. If using multiple ROOT files, it is possible that lxplus will kill the job, so consider using HTCCondor through the .sh and .sub files present. Change paths and necessary.
8. Activate your virtual environment with

```
python3 path/to/venv/bin/activate
```

9. Modify the paths in 27Dtrain.sh to match your own
10. Modify AE-Compression-pytorch/examples/27D/27Dtrain.py to change network and training parameters, such as data paths, filtering and normalization (L47-65), and learning rate and batch decay (L195-200)
11. For 100 epochs, the 'workday' setting in 27DTraining.sub should be sufficient in preventing timeout, but much more than that, the timelimit should be changed.
12. Submit the job from the train_models directory with `condor_submit *sub` and watch progress with `condor_q`

Making Plots

1. Activate your virtual environment with

```
python3 path/to/venv/bin/activate
```

2. After the network of interest has been trained, navigate to the AE-Compression/process_data directory
3. Change the saveDir, path_to_saved_model, and pathToData variables to match where your files are.
4. Run makePreds.py. This should be able to run on lxplus without memory issues, but it will take a few minutes
5. Navigate to the AE-Compression-pytorch/plotting directory
6. To make overlaid, residual, and 2D comparison plots of the data and prediction, run analysisPlots.py, changing the paths to the data, network, and output.
7. To make the correlation corner plots, use the cornerPlots.py script with the same changes made to paths
8. The threshold migration plots are made by the eponymous script, using the passClean function to see if it's a bad jet or not, and passVar to make plots of a specific variable value.
9. To make 1D plots of the variables, use varDistHists.py and change the paths, normalization, and filtering parameters to satisfaction.

Appendix B: Plots

Figure 1: Correlations between the input variables

Figure 2: Correlations between filtered and normalized variables

Figure 3: Losses for filtered and normalized network

Figure 4: Losses for raw data network

Figure 5: Losses for minimally filtered and normalized network

Figure 6: Losses for minimally filtered network

